

Employee's Engagement and Performance: The Case of Sulu State College(SSC)-Sulu

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Abstract

The research findings reveal the following across employees at Sulu State College, Jolo, Sulu: Demographics: The workforce consists of 54% female employees, with 48% holding college degrees. A significant portion (32%) is aged between 31 to 40 years, and 49% have served for 5 years or less, with 62% having regular permanent status. Engagement Levels: Intellectual engagement received an average weighted mean of 4.207 (SD = 0.181), indicating employees generally agree on the level of engagement. Affective engagement had a weighted mean of 4.213 (SD = 0.677), also reflecting agreement among employees. Social engagement yielded a weighted mean of 4.200 (SD = 0.667), showing similar agreement. Task performance scored a weighted mean of 4.261 (SD = 0.140), further indicating agreement. Differences in Engagement: No significant

difference in employee engagement was found based on sex, age, or status of appointment. However, significant differences were observed in engagement levels based on highest educational attainment and length of service. Differences in Performance: Likewise, no significant differences in task performance were seen based on sex, age, or status of appointment. In contrast, significant differences were found related to highest educational attainment and length of service. Correlation between Engagement and Performance: A substantial correlation exists between employee engagement and performance at SSC-Sulu, suggesting that higher engagement is linked to improved performance outcomes. These findings highlight the importance of educational attainment and length of service in influencing both engagement and performance among employees at SSC-Sulu.

Keywords: Employees engagement, employees performance, affective engagement, intellectual engagement

INTRODUCTION

Higher education institutions (HEIs) worldwide are under pressure to improve teaching quality, promote innovation, and prepare graduates for the 21st-century workforce, with faculty engagement being key to these objectives. Engaged faculty members tend to be more effective educators, supportive mentors, and productive researchers, leading to better student outcomes and enhanced institutional reputation (Kuh

et al., 2005). Global higher education trends emphasize the significance of creating environments that support faculty well-being, including work-life balance and professional development.

In the Philippines, HEIs face unique challenges such as limited resources and diverse student needs, with the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) setting standards and promoting quality. National policies, including the K-12 program, highlight the importance of faculty development and research but are often hindered by infrastructure constraints.

Specifically, SSC-Sulu, located in a region with its own socio-political and economic challenges, faces difficulties in faculty recruitment and retention due to geographical isolation and security issues. Understanding these local conditions is essential for interpreting this study's findings and developing relevant recommendations. This research will investigate how local factors influence faculty engagement at SSC-Sulu and its effects on teaching quality, research output, and institutional effectiveness, addressing a gap in research regarding employee engagement and task performance in this context (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008)

METHOD

Research Design

A descriptive-correlational research design method was employed in this study. According to Bless and Higson-Smith, a research design as “a program that guides a researcher in collecting, analyzing and interpreting observed facts.” (1995:63). Moreover, Babbie and Mouton regard research design as the road map or blueprint by which one intends to conduct a research and achieve his/her research goals and objectives.” (2001:75). Thus, this study purported to describe, quantify, and infer as well as to discover significant differences and relationships among variables and to allow the prediction of future events from present knowledge or phenomenon of employees of SSC-Sulu, namely:

- 1) The demographic profile of employee of SSC-Sulu in terms of gender, age, status of appointment, and educational attainment;
- 2) The extent of employees engagement in terms of intellectual engagement, social engagement and affective engagement as well as task performance;
- 3) The significant difference in the extent of faculty's engagement in terms of intellectual engagement, social engagement and affective engagement as well as task performance when data are grouped according to gender, age, status of appointment and educational attainment;
- 4) The degree of correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under employees engagement and performance.

Employees of SSC-Sulu will be the main source of data which will be quantified to answer the research questions in this study. Library and internet research will be the sources of information that will be used to enrich the theoretical and conceptual frameworks of this research. The data from the respondents will be gathered through the use of questionnaires.

Research Locale

This study was conducted among employee of SSC-Sulu during the Fiscal Year 2024. This higher education institution is located in Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu which is under the direct supervision of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED).

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study are the employees of SSC-Sulu who are teaching during this Fiscal Year 2024 regardless of their ranks/positions.

Sampling Design

A non-probability sampling design through purposive sampling method was employed in this study. A total representative of one hundred (100) samples were purposively chosen based on the availability of faculty members of SSC-Sulu. The use of purposive sampling in this study ensured the proper representation of gender, age, civil status, status of appointment and educational attainment.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following procedures were employed in the course of data gathering: A permit to administer the questionnaire was secured from the College President, SSC-Sulu. The researcher had launch and administered the questionnaires personally as well as the retrieval.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire was the main instrument employed to gather data on the extent of engagement and performance among Faculty members at SSC--Sulu. The Faculty engagement questionnaire was adapted and patterned with slight modification from Fletcher (2015) Model on Personal Role Engagement which is based on Soane, et al. (2012) Intellectual, Social and Affective (ISA) Scale. Similarly, task performance will be measured using Koopans et al. (2014) questionnaire.

Soane, et al. (2012) and koopans et al. questionnaires are standardized research instrument with established validity and reliability. Nonetheless, to suit its usability in the local setting, the questionnaire used in this study was subjected to the perusal of two experts from the faculty members of Sulu State College.

The research instrument used in this study consisted of three parts. Part I of the questionnaire which focus on obtaining the demographic profile of the faculty of SSC-Sulu to include gender, age, status of appointment and educational attainment. Part II geared towards obtaining data on the extent of faculty's engagement and performance to include the following dimensions such as Intellectual engagement (3 items), Social engagement (3 items), Affective engagement (3 items), and Task performance (7 items).

Data obtained using these questionnaires were analyzed through a 5-point Likert Scale such as Strongly Agree=5, Agree=4, Undecided=3, Disagree=2, Strongly Disagree=1 will be used for employee's personal role engagement and task performance.

Validity and Reliability

This study was adapted from Fletcher (2015) Model of Personal Role Engagement which is based on Soane, et al. (2012) ISA Scale and Koopans et al. (2014) which are standardized research instrument with established validity and reliability. To suit its usability in the local setting, however, the questionnaire used in this study was subjected to the perusal of at least two experts from Sulu State College.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistical tools were appropriately employed in the treatment of data gathered for this study, namely:

- 1) For research problem number one 1, frequency counts and percentage will be employed to determine the demographic profile of faculty of SSC-Sulu;
- 2) For research problem number two 2, mean and standard deviation will be employed to determine the extent of engagement and performance of Faculties;
- 3) For research problem number 3, t-test for independent samples will be employed to determine the significant differences in the extent of engagement and performance when data are grouped according

to gender; and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) will be employed to determine the significant differences when data are grouped according to age, status of appointment and educational attainment.

- 4) For research question number 4, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r) will be employed to determine the degree of correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under engagement and performance.

The following rating scales intervals will be adopted in the analyses of the results of the computations obtained from the use of both descriptive and inferential statistical tools:

Rating Scales Interval on the extent of personal role engagement and task performance of employees based on 5-point Likert's Scale:

Point	Scale Value	Descriptors
5	4.50- 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50- 4.49	Agree
3	2.50- 3.49	Undecided
2	1.50- 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00- 1.49	Strongly Disagree

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The main purpose of the study was to assess the relationship between engagement and performance of employees in Sulu State College, Jolo, Sulu. In order to meet the purpose, this chapter discusses demographic profile of the respondents, descriptive and inferential statistics allowed the study to consolidate and summarize the data collected.

Thus, to inspect the extent of engagement and Performance of employee at SSC-Sulu in terms of: Intellectual engagement; Affective engagement; Social engagement; and Task performance, adopted questionnaire was used for employees to give their feedbacks. 100 questionnaires were distributed at SSC-Sulu. From the total number of questionnaires distributed to employees all (100) were fully answered and returned; finally, the researcher had secured 100 responded questionnaires. Therefore, the questionnaires collected is 100% response rate.

1. Profile of the Employees' Respondents

In terms of sex

Out of 100 employees' respondents in Sulu State College, Jolo, Sulu, 46.0 percent are male respondents and 54.0 percent are female respondents. In this study, majority of the respondents are female.

In terms of Age bracket

Thirty-two (32) percent of the employees were 31 years old to 40 years old, followed by the 41 years old to 50 years old with a percentage of 26.0 percent, and 23 percent were age 30 years old & below. On the lowest were those on the senior category with a percentage of 19.0 percent. Majority of the employees' respondents are from 31 to 40 years of age.

Status of Appointment

Sixty-two (62) percent of the employees were permanent in status, followed by temporary in status of employees with a percentage of 23.0 percent, and 15.0 percent were contractual or job order employees. Majority of the employees' respondents are permanent in their status of appointment.

In terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Almost 50 percent of the employees' respondents were Bachelor's degree holders, followed by those Bachelor's degree with master's units with a frequency of 25 or 25.0 percent, 14.0 percent of employees' respondents were master's degree, 9.0 percent are employees with doctoral units, and those respondents with doctorate degree were at the lowest with a frequency of four or 4.0 percent. The employees' respondents could still elevate their educational attainment to increase the number of those having doctorate degrees.

In terms of Length of Service

Forty-nine or 49.0 percent being the greater number of the employees in Sulu State College, Jolo, Sulu were in the service for 5 years and less, 28.0 percent were employees had been working from 6 years to 10 years, and the smallest number of the employees were 23.0 percent who were in the service for 11 years and more. This means that most of the respondents were newly hired employees.

2. The extent of engagement and performance of employee at SSC-Sulu in terms of:

- 2.1 Intellectual engagement;
- 2.2 Affective engagement;
- 2.3 Social engagement; and
- 2.4 Task performance

2.1. In terms of Intellectual engagement

Intellectual engagement is one of the engagements and performance of employee at SSC-Sulu and the result is shown in Table 2.1. There are three (3) questions presented to evaluate this Intellectual engagement and the response are summarized in the table in the next page.

**Table 2.1
Engagement and performance of the Employee in terms of Intellectual Engagement**

Statement	Mean	S.D.	Description
Inspires and motivates me to achieve my goals.	4.510	0.522	Strongly Agree
Encourages me to think creatively and come up with new ideas.	4.240	0.726	Agree
Provides a clear vision for the organization and communicates it effectively.	3.870	0.884	Agree
Total	4.207	0.181	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50 – 4.49 = Agree; (3) 2.50 – 3.49 = Undecided; (2) 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; (1) 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 2.1 shows the extent of engagement and performance in terms of Intellectual engagement. Under this group, employees' responses have total weighted mean score of 4.207 with standard deviation of 0.181 which is rated as **Agree**. This result indicates that employee-respondents involved in this study believed

that Knowledgeable engagement will inspire and motivates them to achieve the institutional goals and provides to think creatively and come up with best ideas.

2.2. In terms of Affective engagement

Affective engagement is the second of the engagement and performance of employee at SSC-Sulu and the result is showed in Table 2.2. There are three (3) questions presented to evaluate this Affective engagement and the response are summarized in the table below.

Table 2.2
Engagement and performance of the Employee in terms of Affective Engagement

Statement	Mean	S.D.	Description
I share the same work values as my colleagues	4.350	0.626	Agree
I share the same work goals as my colleagues	4.210	0.701	Agree
I share the same work attitudes as my colleagues	4.080	0.706	Agree
Total	4.213	0.677	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50 – 4.49 = Agree; (3) 2.50 – 3.49 = Undecided; (2) 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; (1) 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Out of 100 respondents, employees agreed on all the statement of the engagement and performance of employee in terms of Affective engagement. The employee shares the same work values, goals and attitudes as their colleagues.

Generally, the employee-respondents obtained a weighted mean score of 4.213 with standard deviation of 0.677 which is rated as “Agree” on the extent of engagement and performance of respondents in terms of Affective engagement. This means that employees adopts an open-door policy where they feel comfortable sharing their thoughts with co-workers.

2.3. In terms of Social engagement

Social engagement is the third of the engagement and performance of employee at SSC-Sulu and the result is showed in Table 2.3. There are three (3) questions presented to evaluate this Social engagement and the response are summarized in the table below.

Table 2.3
Engagement and performance of the Employee in terms of Social engagement

Statement	Mean	S.D.	Description
I am enthusiastic in my work	4.400	0.636	Agree
I feel positive about my work	3.890	0.803	Agree
I feel energetic in my work	4.310	0.563	Agree
Total	4.200	0.667	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50 – 4.49 = Agree; (3) 2.50 – 3.49 = Undecided; (2) 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; (1) 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Out of 100 respondents, employees Agreed on all the statement of the engagement and performance of employee in terms of Social engagement with a mean of 4.200 and a standard deviation of 0.667. Majority of the employees are dedicated, confident and energetic in their work.

2.4. In terms of Task performance

Task performance is the fourth of the engagement and performance of employee at SSC-Sulu and the result is showed in Table 2.4. There are seven (7) questions presented to evaluate this Task performance and the response are summarized in the table below.

Table 2.4
Engagement and performance of the Employee in terms of Task performance

Statement	Mean	S.D.	Description
I managed to plan my work so that it was done on time	4.390	0.567	Agree
My planning was optimal.	3.790	0.844	Agree
I kept in mind the results that I had to achieve in my work.	4.690	0.506	Strongly Agree
I was able to separate main issues from side issues at work.	3.970	0.797	Agree
I knew how to set the right priorities.	4.520	0.674	Strongly Agree
I was able to perform my work well with minimal time and effort.	3.970	0.870	Agree
Collaboration with others was very productive.	4.500	0.644	Strongly Agree
Total	4.261	0.140	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50 – 4.49 = Agree; (3) 2.50 – 3.49 = Undecided; (2) 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; (1) 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Out of 100 employees' respondents, 43 percent of them Strongly Agreed on the statements number 3, 5 and 7 of the Engagement and performance of Employee in terms of Task performance. Result means that the employees know how to set the right priorities to perform and achieve the results of their task.

However, 57 percent of the employees' responses Agree on the statements number 1, 2, 4, and 6. Employees managed to plan their work so that it is done on time and able to perform their work well with minimal time and effort.

Generally, the employee-respondents obtained an overall weighted mean score of 4.261 with standard deviation of 0.140 which is rated as "Agree" on the extent of the Engagement and performance of Employee in terms of Task performance.

3. The significant difference on the extent of Engagement and performance of Employees at SSC-Sulu when respondents are grouped according to sex, age, status of appointment, highest educational attainment and length of service

3.1. Engagement of Employee

3.1.A. According to Sex

Table 3.1.A shows the significant difference on the responses of the respondents on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to sex.

It can be gleaned from this table 3.1.A that the t-values of 0.631 is less than the t-critical value of 2.119 is indeed NOT Significant at alpha 0.05. The null hypothesis is accepted. This means that the responses of male and female employee-respondents are almost same level of extent towards the engagement of the employees to their work.

Table 3.1.A. Significant difference on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to their sex

Sex	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t-Comp. Value	t-Crit. Value	Description	Interpretation
Female	4.241	0.194	0.074	0.631	2.119	Accept	Not Significant
Male	4.167	0.294				H ₀	

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.1.B. According to Age

Table 3.1.B presents the differences on the responses of the respondents on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to age. It can be gleaned from this table that F-value of 0.107 is less than the F-critical value of 2.901 is indeed NOT Significant at alpha 0.05. This means that even though employee-respondents vary in age range, yet they do not differ in their engagement to perform their work well.

Table 3.1.B. Significant difference on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to their age

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F	crit	Decision	Interpretation
Between Groups	0.020	3	0.007	0.107	2.901	Accept	Not Significant
Within Groups	1.951	32	0.061			H ₀	
Total	1.971	35					

alpha set at 0.05 level of confidence

3.1.C. According to Status of Appointment

Table 3.1.C presents the differences on the responses of the respondents on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to status of appointment. It can be gleaned from this table that F-value of 0.633 is less than the F-critical value of 3.403 is indeed NOT Significant at alpha 0.05. Therefore, we have evidence to Accept the null hypothesis.

Table 3.1.C. Significant difference on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to their status of appointment

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F	F-crit	Decision	Interpretation

Between Groups	0.085	2	0.042	0.633	.403	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Within Groups	1.604	24	0.067				
Total	1.688	26					

alpha set at 0.05 level of confidence

3.1.D. According to Highest Educational Attainment

Table 3.1.D presents the differences on the responses of the respondents on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to their highest educational attainment. It can be seen from this table that F-value of 7.620 is greater than the F-critical value of 2.606, is indeed Significant at alpha 0.05. This means that employee-respondents having different level in educational attainment, may probably have different level of knowledge in engagement on their work.

Table 3.1.D. Significant difference on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to their highest educational attainment

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F	F-crit	Decision	Interpretation
Between Groups	2.424	4	0.606	7.620	2.606	Reject H ₀	Significant
Within Groups	3.181	40	0.080				
Total	5.604	44					

alpha set at 0.05 level of confidence

3.1.E. According to Length of Service

Table 3.1.E presents the differences on the responses of the respondents on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to their Length of Service. It can be seen from this table that F-value of 9.209 is greater than the F-critical value of 3.403, is indeed Significant at alpha 0.05. This means that employee-respondents having more years in experience are more positive about their work.

Table 3.1.E. Significant difference on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to their Length of Service

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F	F-crit	Decision	Interpretation
Between Groups	1.171	2	0.586	9.209	3.403	Reject	Significant

Within Groups	1.526	24	0.064			H ₀
Total	2.697	26				

alpha set at 0.05 level of confidence

3.2. Performance of Employee

3.2.A. According to Sex

Table 3.2.A shows the significant difference on the responses of the respondents on the extent of task performance of Employees when data are grouped according to sex.

Table 3.2.A. Significant difference on the extent of performance of Employees when data are grouped according to their sex

Sex	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	Comp. Value	-Crit. Value	Description	Interpretation
Female	.323	.327	0.134	0.703	2.179	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Male	.189	.380					

*Significant at alpha 0.05

It can be gleaned from this table 3.1.A that the t-values of 0.703 is less than the t-critical value of 2.179 is indeed NOT Significant at alpha 0.05. The null hypothesis is accepted. This means that the responses of male and female employee-respondents are almost same level of extent towards the task performance of the employees to their work.

3.2.B. According to Age

Table 3.2.B presents the differences on the responses of the respondents on the extent of task performance of Employees when data are grouped according to age. It can be gleaned from this table that F-value of 0.018 is less than the F-critical value of 3.009 is indeed NOT Significant at alpha 0.05. This means that even though employee-respondents vary in age range, yet they do not differ in their task to perform and manage their work.

Table 3.2.B. Significant difference on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to their age

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F	F-crit	Decision	Interpretation

Between Groups	0.007	3	0.002	0.018	0.009	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Within Groups	3.116	24	0.130				
Total	3.123	27					

alpha set at 0.05 level of confidence

3.2.C. According to Status of Appointment

Table 3.2.C presents the differences on the responses of the respondents on the extent of task performance of Employees when data are grouped according to status of appointment. It can be gleaned from this table that F-value of 0.228 is less than the F-critical value of 3.555 is indeed NOT Significant at alpha 0.05. Therefore, we have evidence to Accept the null hypothesis.

Table 3.2.C. Significant difference on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to their status of appointment

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F	F-crit	Decision	Interpretation
Between Groups	0.056	2	0.028	0.228	3.555	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Within Groups	2.208	18	0.123				
Total	2.264	20					

alpha set at 0.05 level of confidence

3.2.D. According to Highest Educational Attainment

Table 3.2.D presents the differences on the responses of the respondents on the extent of task performance of Employees when data are grouped according to their highest educational attainment. It can be seen from this table that F-value of 8.276 is greater than the F-critical value of 2.690 is indeed Significant at alpha 0.05. This means that employee-respondents having different level in educational attainment, may probably have different strategies in planning about their task so that it will be done on time.

Table 3.2.D. Significant difference on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to their highest educational attainment

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean	F	F-crit	Decision	Interpretation

			qua res				
Between Groups	3.772	4	.94 3	276.690	reject H ₀	significant	
Within Groups	3.419	30	.11 4				
Total	7.191	34					

alpha set at 0.05 level of confidence

3.2.E. According to Length of Service

Table 3.2.E presents the differences on the responses of the respondents on the extent of task performance of Employees when data are grouped according to their Length of Service. It can be seen from this table that F-value of 5.934 is greater than the F-critical value of 3.403 is indeed Significant at alpha 0.05. This means that employee-respondents having more years in experience can perform well with minimal time and effort compared less years of work experience.

Table 3.2.E. Significant difference on the extent of Engagement of Employees when data are grouped according to their Length of Service

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F	F-crit	Decision	Interpretation
Between Groups	.534	2	.267	5.934	3.555	Reject H ₀	Significant
Within Groups	.327	8	.041				
Total	.861	10					

* alpha set at 0.05 level of confidence

4. The significant correlation between engagement and performance of employees at SSC—Sulu

Table 4 shows the significant correlation between engagement and performance of employees at SSC--Sulu. It can be gleaned from this table that computed Pearson r Correlation Coefficients is 0.6131 between these variables at alpha 0.05 level of significance is Substantial Relationship. This result indicates that engagement of employees to focus, concentrate and pay attention to their work is significantly related to their performance in accomplishing their task.

Table 4. The significant correlation between engagement and performance of employees

	Pearson r Correlation	
	Performance of Employee	Interpretation
Engagement of Employee	0.6131	Substantial Relationship

Correlation Coefficient is significant at alpha 0.05
Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from De Vaus's (2002): 0.10-0.29 =Low; 0.30-0.49 =Moderate; 0.50-0.69 =Substantial; 0.70-0.89 =Very Strong; 0.90-0.99 =Near Perfect; 1.00 = Perfect Relationship

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